

GENESIS 4TH GENERATION / NOMADICITY / GESTURE EMULATION

REAL-TIME CORDIS-ANIMA PHYSICAL MODELING AND HIGH PERFORMANCE FORCE-FEEDBACK INTERACTION WITHIN THE *HÉLICANTHE* WORKSTATION

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ABSTRACT

We present news developments and their integration within the ACROE's *Hélicanthe creative workstation*. These improve the concepts and technologies previously implemented in the CORDIS-ANIMA formalism, the GENESIS software and the TELLURIS station for interactive multisensory simulation of physical objects, TELLURIS including the ACROE's haptic systems, "*Transducteurs Gestuels Rétroactifs*" (TGR).

After a brief review of the theoretical and technological bases, we present:

1) the new prototype of the fourth generation of GENESIS dedicated to modeling for real time with force feedback systems, G-IV.

2) a new principle of *gestural emulation* allowing, in the absence of force feedback devices and in non real time, to design physics-based instruments models to be simulated on real time platforms equipped with TGRs.

Finally we illustrate through the musical artwork *Quetzalcoatl* (Cadoz, 2018) composed on *Hélicanthe*, new ways of musical dialogues: (i) between real gestures on haptic devices and emulated ones; (ii) between several instrumentalists playing on two coupled TGRs.

We conclude on the perspective of "*writing the gesture*" which is by such advancements.

1. INTRODUCTION

The *Hélicanthe* Platform (Figure 1) is a new real-time interactive platform which integrates the five basic technologies developed by ACROE into a complete tool for multi-sensory musical and artistic creation:

- CORDIS-ANIMA: a modular physical modeling and simulation formalism for multi-sensory responsive simulation of physical objects [1,2],
- TGR: "*Transducteur Gestuel Rétroactif*", mechatronical interface for force feedback gestural

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interaction [3,4],

- TELLURIS: which integrates TGRs and a powerful and reactive computer (Figure 2),
- GENESIS: a software environment dedicated to physical modeling for sound and musical creation [5,6], and in particular its new version G-IV,
- MIMESIS: a physical modeling software environment for Computer Animation. [7].
- 24-channels audio and a multi video projection.

Figure 1. The *Hélicanthe* Platform. Spatial organisation adopted for the 24 loudspeakers.

Figure 2. TELLURIS functional diagram: the real-time simulator (red), the force feedback gestural system with mechanics (blue) and electronics (white), and the audio and video output peripherals.

In this article, we tackle the question of the "nomadcity" of technically very demanding systems, as is the case of high-performance force feedback devices, ie the possibility of using their fundamental functionalities without degradation, apart from fixed (sedentary) reference platforms, for example with a simple laptop.

First, we present the first prototype of the fourth generation of GENESIS, the G-IV software environment developed by ACROE, dedicated to real-time CORDIS-ANIMA modeling and simulation. We then introduce the principle of “Gestural Emulation”, by which force feedback gestural devices and instrumental gestures are themselves simulated by physical models. Such emulation allows designing instrumental models, *in the absence of TGRs and in non-real time mode*, to later run *in real time with force feedback devices*. By way of such emulation, we are able to foresee, off-line, future real time situations with real TGRs and real gestures. Such a “Gestural Emulation”, beyond its predictive function, can coexist with real TGRs and gestures, within a real-virtual duet. In addition, emulated gestures can be applied to real TGRs themselves. It follows that the instrumentalist will perceive them in his-her fingers and will be able to learn, accompany or thwart them, improve or transform them.

The last session of the paper is devoted to the musical artwork *Quetzalcoatl* (Cadoz, 2018), composed on the *Hélicanthe* workstation, as a new musical experience on which all these modalities are implemented. The piece illustrated a mix of real time models and non real-time ones. It also proposes an “inter-instrumentality situation” by which two instrumentalists play together on the same shared instrument, feeling each others’ gestures, and also a mix of real gestures and emulated gestures.

2. NECESSARY REQUIREMENTS FOR MULTI-SENSORY-MOTOR SIMULATION

2.1. Performance of Force Feedback Gestural Devices

Force feedback in multisensory-motor simulation must fulfill exigent requirements as the proprio-kinesthetic sensori-motor modality is very sophisticated. It combines lot of features such as dynamics, resolutions, sufficient number of degrees of freedom, distributed in complex spaces and versatile geometries, etc.

The properties of the haptic devices hence depend on several parameters: inertia, elasticity of moving components, frictions of joints and guides; end effectors morphologies, resolution and ambitus of position sensors and of the forces produced by actuators, frequency bandwidths and temporal latencies, etc. [8,9].

The ACROE TGRs were primarily designed by taking into account all these parameters at their higher level of performance with the concern to be used as a “reference” and “metrological” system for qualitative and quantitative scientific and musical research on gestures.

As an example, we shown in [10], within an experiment on musical bowing gestures that some scaling down on some parameters are possible without breaking down the relevant features of the gesture, but conversely that some others must be kept at the highest quality to reach a musical level of playability and believability of the virtual musical instrument.

2.2. The performance of the simulation

2.2.1. Algorithmic performance - performance of computation

Beside the TGR’s performance, the efficiency of the simulation loops is also of a great importance. It takes place primarily in the optimality of the algorithms. Such optimality is not simple to reach as it is at the crossing point between at least three constraints: (1) “axiomatic” properties, i.e. to be more general as possible, (2) the widest possible coverage of the field, (3) the computation efficiency itself. The CORDIS-ANIMA formalism (§3.1) took care of all of these through: (1) the minimalism of the simulation language elements; (2) the choice of basic Newtonian principles and the most robust discretization schemes, (3) the minimalism of the number of operations per algorithmic modules.

There are four conditions for the calculation process:

- The need of an absolutely regular time base at all levels of the simulation chain (gestural input signals, gestural physical simulation, acoustic physical simulation, gestural, audio and visual outputs). If there is an absence of regular time basis, the notions of speed and acceleration, are lost, i.e. to the differential calculus in time itself.

- The execution of the whole simulation loop must be achieved within the time interval of a simulation step. This simulation step is regulated on one hand by the numerical stability of the discrete algorithms and on the other hand by the Shannon frequency required to obtain the desired dynamics.

- The need of synchronism, that is to say of the unequivocal correspondence between the time of input T_i and the time of output T_j of the algorithm whatever the simulation step imposed by the algorithm.

- That of the minimum latency, expressed in number of samples, between the input and output samples, particular on the haptic system.

The real-time computer architectures of ACROE implement a regular time step from 5kHz to 44.1 kHz, synchronized on an hardware clock, with the minimum latency of 1 sample between inputs and outputs [11].

2.2.2. Relevance of the model

Although it is impossible to define, *in abstracto*, what could mean “relevance of the model”, we may have in mind some basic guidelines. Let’s take the example of a musical timbral richness. The relevance of the model cannot be associated univocally to its complexity in terms of number of elements generating the acoustical phenomenon, and vice-versa. This leads, generally speaking, that we must be able to simulate as many optimal components as possible with a given computational tool.

2.3. “Nomadicity”

Let us assume that we have at our disposal all the best conditions in terms of TGRs and in terms of algorithms, and in terms of simulation platforms, such as those discussed above. Nevertheless, it remains that: *It is absolutely legitimate to wish to simulate the very largest physical structures, even in non-real time, and/or structures played by a huge number of instrumentalists through a incredible variety of TGRs!*

Therefore, it is of a primary importance to be able to co-articulate what can be done “off-real-time” and what can be done “on-line and in real time”, for example with a limited number of high quality TGRs or computers. Hence, we consider that articulating fluently “on-line” performances and “off-line” simulations is a basic functionality of a creation tool called its “nomadicity”.

3. GENESIS FOURTH GENERATION

3.1. Reminders: The CORDIS-ANIMA formalism ¹

Figure 3. From Music V to CORDIS-ANIMA.

The CORDIS-ANIMA (CA) modeling and simulation formalism is grounded on block modeling principle as initiated by Mathews in *Music V* [11] (Figure 3. Left). It differs fundamentally because the relationships between modules are, by principle and structurally, bidirectional (Figure 3. Right). Indeed, they represent physical interactions satisfying the action-reaction Newtonian principle. One of their mathematical representation is by pairs of dual variables: one called “intensive” (VI), such as force, the other called “extensive” (VE) such as position or velocity.

The axiomatic of CORDIS-ANIMA is based on reverse pairs of oriented relationships. Let’s consider two categories of data flow: force (F as VI) and position (X as the chosen VE). The CORDIS-ANIMA basic language entity is the “Communication Point”, through which a pair {F, X} is circulating. There are two types of Communication Points: <M> Point, that inputs F and outputs X, and <L> Point, that inputs X and outputs F.

The rules to connect two Communication Points derive from their syntax: (a) only two different types of Points can be connected; (b) only VI are additive, multiple <L> points can be connected to a single <M> Point and only one <M> point can be connected to an <L> Point.

Consequently, two types of modules are introduced in the formal CORDIS-ANIMA system:

- one called <MAT> element, for Material element, with only one <M> Communication Point,
- and the other, called <LIA> element, for Link element, having two <L> Communication Points.

Then, a CORDIS-ANIMA object is an assembly of <MAT> and <LIA> elements, that takes the form of a network, called “CORDIS-ANIMA Network”, on which the nodes are <MAT> and bonds are <LIA>.

In order to simplify the graphical representation, the pair of bonds are represented by a single line (Figure 4).

3.1.1. CORDIS-ANIMA is multisensory by nature

The properties considered in CA are nor perceptual (auditory, visual or haptic) but physical (inertia, elasticity, friction, etc.).

The simulation algorithms are distributed in <MAT> and <LIA> modules and compute, at each time step, the physical behaviors of such “Virtual Matter”, lumped within the CA network.

The relationship to sensorialities occurs only downstream of the physical simulation: extraction of auditory signals from selected <M> points, pairs of input-output haptic signals from selected <L> points, visual 3D rendering from the movements of all (or selected) <MAT> elements.

The “imaging” issue consists here in the mixing of these three multi sensory-motor output processes.

3.1.2. Computational “modules” and simulation loop

Simulations take place on modules, that correspond exactly to the formal elements <MAT> and <LIA>.

At each step, <MAT> modules compute positions from forces, satisfying the additivity on forces, and <LIA> modules compute pairs of forces from pairs of positions, satisfying the Newton action-reaction principle.

The simulation loop relies on the duality of <MAT> and <LIA> modules. First, each simulation step is composed of two phases, the <MAT> and <LIA> phases. Second, the choices of the discrete algorithms in each <MAT> and <LIA> modules and the temporal sequencing between <MAT> and <LIA> phases implement a robust symplectic computation scheme, which allows to control accurately the energy consistency over long durations.

3.2. Reminders on GENESIS

GENESIS is the software environment that allows to design CORDIS-ANIMA Networks, for sound and music, by direct interactive manipulation of <MAT> and <LIA> modules and their respective physical parameters (Figure 4). GENESIS provides to the user high-level functionalities: various situations of simulations, of hearing, of visualizing, of structures analysis (modal, metrological issues, etc.); PNSL modeling language to accompany GUI-based modeling, etc.

¹ For the full description of the CORDIS-ANIMA formalism, see [2]

The designing process is split in 3 steps: (1) the design of the CA model, (2) the simulation step and (3) the listening and the visualization of the results. Noticeably, all of these steps are off-line and in non-real time. The new version G-IV presented in §3.3 and the “Gestural Emulator” presented in §4, allows to go beyond this situation.

Figure 4. The GENESIS workbench.

3.3. GENESIS – IV

G-IV is the new prototype, recently designed by the ACROE’s software development team headed by Nicolas Castagné.

It contains the entire GENESIS functionalities previously implemented. As such, it is able to accept any models designed with the previous versions.

It greatly improves the models by implementing new processes for *on-line real-time* simulation. So doing, it runs on the *Hélicanthe* Workstation, with its real time simulator and high quality force feedback devices.

Extending GENESIS with real time capabilities including TGR is not a simple technical mooring.

First, of course, the user can declare a TGR as a CA module within a CA network. Consistently with CA formalism, TGR is nothing more than a <MAT> module. From the user modeling point of view, nothing is changed. From the simulation one, all the simulation algorithms remain coherent: the instrumentalist will act on, and receive forces from the simulation, as usual.

A second major contribution is that G-IV includes functionalities for segmenting a CA physical network in several parts, preserving the physical consistency of the whole model. For that, it contains methods to adapt the physical flows (in frequencies, geometry, forces etc.) between these different sub-parts in respect with energy and physical power they convey.

Let us take the case of the instrumental musical situation. In his-her modeling activity, the user has the option to separate models in two parts, for example:

- one that corresponds to the mechanical parts close to the gestures (i.e. to the TGRs), exhibiting lower frequencies than acoustical ones,
- and one that corresponds to the acoustical parts.

The user can choose the simulation frequencies for each part, usually 44.1kHz for vibrating parts and about

1 to 10kHz for gestural part. One of the consequences is that the physical parameters of each simulated module are automatically adjusted in order to preserve its physical consistency of the modules and of the relationship between the two parts. Assume that the user first designed a CA model in GENESIS-3 adjusting its parameters for 44.1kHz. Then, after he-she separates this model in two parts running at different frequencies, the behaviors of the first non-separated model are entirely preserved: this means that his-her previous designing activity remains integrally valid.

4. “GESTURAL EMULATION “ – REFLECTIVE METROLOGY

4.1. “Gestural Emulation “

We present now the principle of “Gestural Emulation”, aiming to design force feedback real-time CA models, but off-line, in the absence of TGR and in non real-time (Figure 5).

The principle consists in substituting the real TGR *and the gestures applied on it* by CA models. To model the TGR device requires a precise knowledge of the real device, which is not that simple.

Figure 5. “Gestural Emulation “ / TGR Emulation.

4.1.1. TGR Emulation

A TGR device is characterized by mechanical properties (§2.1) : inertia, stiffness, linear and non-linear frictions, of their components or emerging of their morphologies. Figure 6 shows one ACROE TGR device of 12 degrees of freedom called CRM and how it is connected to a CORDIS-ANIMA model. On the right of Figure 6 the <MAT> element represents the TGR within CA.

Figure 6. The “Clavier Rétroactif Modulaire” (CRM) ACROE - ERGOS Technologies.

One can first observe that, at rest, the TGR key is in a low position. This indicates the presence of a weight, and thus of an inertia. The weight can be measured with a simple weighing system as shown below (Figure 7):

Figure 7. Weighing system of a TGR's key.

A simplified model of a TGR's slice can be a CA MAS with a Mtgr inertia value. However, it is not what is observed: when a TGR key is moved toward another position, it will stay at rest while the device oscillates very slightly and returns to its starting rest position: all this happens as if there are stiffness and damper forces. Adding a CA REF module², with stiffness Ktgr and damping Ztgr parameters can model this observation.

With appropriate metrological methods, one can estimate the Ktgr, et Ztgr values. Then, a first CA model of the TGR could be a CEL module³, with chosen values for its parameters, Mtgr, Ktgr, et Ztgr. Then the behaviors of the real key and of its so-designed model can be compared point-to-point at any time. This simplest model constitutes the first step of an iterative process, described in §4.2, and called "Reflective Metrology".

4.1.2. Gesture Emulation

With GENESIS, off-line and in absence of gestural action, materials element are put in motion from their initial values (X0 and V0). This corresponds to an initial quantum of energy applied to the system. During the simulation, this energy is dissipated⁴ through viscous elements till the rest state.

Then : "how to represent (write) the conditions causing the occurrence of events, i.e. of temporal singularities, in a universe where the processes run determinedly from laws prescribed at the beginning of all things?"

Create the event

The simplest way to create an event, in such physical but virtual universe, is to provoke the collisions between two particles by means of the simplest non-linear interaction called BUT⁵ (§3.2). Let the first particle being at the

position "0" and the second at X0 with an initial negative velocity V0. The collision will occurs exactly at the time $T0 = X0/V0$. This means that the date of the event was born from initial conditions by the fact of non-linearities.

Figure 8. The "Striker" / The "Struck". The small yellow ball is the mass simulating the "Striker". It is linked to the "Struck" (yellow ball at the bottom) by a BUT module (red) simulating an oriented collision, with a contact stiffness and viscosity (K, Z). The struck is connected to a fixed point (green) by a REF module (spring and friction). This constitutes an elementary oscillator (the simplest instrument we can imagine).

In the previous situation (Figure 8), particle 1, "the struck", is passive and particle 2, "the striker" is active. Launching a striker with adequate initial conditions toward a mass, for example the mass of the TGR Emulator, initiates its movement at a chosen time T, with a precise velocity. The continuation of the movement is "ballistic": it no longer depends of the strike. Thus, we get the simplest gestural emulator.

Ballistic gesture

Let's simply consider an instrumentalist as a mechanical system composed of passive articulated rigid solids (the skeleton) and muscles (actuators) controlled by the mind. Without seeking to model biological, physiological, or neuronal issues of the gesture, it can be considered as composed of two dual counterparts: one of structural permanent properties and another of contingent acts considered as events, the "evenemential" part (Figure 9).

An example could be again a CA CEL oscillator: after being launched, the continuation of the movement no longer depends on the hit as in a ballistic motion. It could be possible to design more complex models. However, the duality between a triggering process and a ballistic flowing in the gesture suggests the ultimate nature of the gestural acts as "mind events", upstream of the physical, physiological or biological contingencies.

Such paradigm shift will be the step toward a physics-based narrative gesture.

² A CORDIS-ANIMA REF module calculates the pairs of opposite forces produced by a virtual damped spring from the positions and velocities of two linked <MAT>

³ A CORDIS-ANIMA CEL module combines MAS and REF and simulates the second order mechanical oscillator.

⁴ Apart from situations of divergence which we do not consider here.

⁵ A CORDIS-ANIMA BUT

Figure 9. Gesture Modeling: Evenemential / Structural duality.

Narrative Gesture

We call “narrative gesture”, or more precisely the narrative part of the emulated gesture, the events that must be carried out over time in order to decide precisely, at each instant, the value of a chosen variable. Here, the variable is the position of the material point representing the TGR or its emulator.

Within the CORDIS-ANIMA and TGRs framework, this means: “how to generate the movement of a TGR or its emulator so that it follows an arbitrarily chosen narrative profile?”

Indeed, this profile can be described by a sequence of pairs of instant and positions called “GN”, as following:

$$GN = (T_i, X_i) ; i \in \mathbb{N} \quad (1)$$

In the next paragraph, we propose a generation method based on the generalization of the one used previously to create the event.

Throwing of low inertia particles at high velocity

In the previous paragraph, we introduced a striker which was launched against the mass of the TGR Emulator under correct initial conditions. At the chosen time T, it started to move in the same direction as the striker. Its velocity can be calculated with the movement quantity and energy conservation equations of the system composed by the two colliding particles. Collisions are considered without dissipation.

Let m and M the respective inertia of the striker and the struck; v and V their velocities before the collision; v' and V' the velocities after the collision.

With the following initial conditions: {X0=0 ; V0=0} for the struck; positive position x0 with negative initial velocity v0 for the striker, in one dimension, it comes:

$$\begin{cases} v' = \frac{(m - M)v + 2MV}{m + M} \\ V' = \frac{2mv + (M - m)V}{m + M} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Let us take the value of the inertia of the striker much smaller than that of the struck and the velocity of the striker much greater than that of the struck. It comes:

$$\begin{cases} v' \approx -v \\ V' \approx V + 2 \frac{m}{M} v \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The striker bounces and goes in the opposite direction with a velocity equal to the incident one while the velocity of the struck increases of⁶:

$$\Delta V = 2 \frac{m}{M} v \quad (4)$$

By this way, we are able to compute exactly the value of the velocity v_i of the striker particle at each time T_i. In addition, with a high velocity “v_i” for the striker, the error on the time T of the impact becomes negligible, whatever is the position of the struck, which could be oscillating. By launching the striker from a very high distance and a very high velocity, we can get the instant of the impact as precisely as we want. That is a very relevant condition to “draw” the profile of the narrative gesture as close as possible to which we have in mind.

The “Ergons”

We call “ergons” such particles having a very small inertia and a high velocity, hence a non-negligible energy. Note that we can tune this energy through the m/M ratio and the velocity v, so as to be at the scale of the gestural energy.

To change the direction of the ergon’s effect on the struck - above and below, positive or negative - we then define ergons “+” and ergons “-“, a kind of duplet of “matter” and “anti-matter”.

It comes that, by throwing chosen “positive” and “negative” ergons along time, we are able to obtain off time, with the Emulated TGR, exactly the movement profile we seek. Moreover, we can hence emulate a real gesture applied to the real TGR, and obtain off-time the same exact movement we have in real time.

The method can be generalized to more complex models of TGR than a CEL (the struck) after having a right analytical model of it, by means of the metrological reflective methodology described in §4.2.

By this way, we are able to physically simulate what we called in [12] “ergotic gestures”. Such “simulated ergotic gestures” can take their rightful place in a non real time and off-line simulations and in addition, are able to play together with real ergotic ones.

4.2. Reflective Metrology

The reflective metrology method consists in applying simultaneously the simulated ergotic gestures to the simulated TGR and to the real TGR in absence of real instrumentalist.

In case of the simulated and real TGR were absolutely identical, since they are submitted to identical gestures, they should exhibit exactly the same movement.

⁶ Note that it complies with the conservation of the movement quantity of the whole system.

To reach such results, several steps must be walked over until the model can be considered as right.

First, a real TGR calibration stage, in order to master the real-virtual correspondence of the values of the variables (forces, velocities and positions) and that of parameters values (inertia, stiffness, viscosity). And second, the refinement of the virtual model of the TGR, by adding physical elements able to reconstitute, for example, the vibrating modes measured on the real ones. We can use here the CORDIS-ANIMA modal analyzer.

Reflective metrology allows simultaneously: to simulate the real TGR so as to get knowledge on it and to know the real TGR so as to simulate it. Finally, once achieved, the model becomes a means to calibrate the real TGRs. Such “*specular iterative process*” is a predominant paradigm that grounds permanently our work [13]. It constitutes, for us, a “virtuous circle” whose centrifugal force is a creative force.

5. QUETZALCOATL - SPECULAR AND INTER INSTRUMENTALITY

Figure 10. Visualization of simulation in *Quetzalcoatl*. The yellow particles are “ergons”, the blue ones are the 10,000 independent oscillators.

The musical piece *Quetzalcoatl*⁷ is entirely designed with GENESIS (Figure 10). It sets up a first way of duality: a very huge CORDIS-ANIMA model composed of more than 230,000 modules, which is simulated in non real time, and a sub-part of this model which can be simulated and controlled by 12 keys of the TGR in real time. These two parts are played on the *Hélicanthe* Workstation. During the performance, the pre-computed part is displayed on the 24 audio channels of a sound dome in synchronicity with the visual display of the 3D movements of all the <MAT> modules (cf. §5.1.).

GENESIS allows a real time interactive navigation within the 3D visualized scene.

The performance itself consists on the playing of two instrumentalists on two *real* TGR and, last but not the least: the TGR are coupled, allowing instrumentalists to play *together* on a shared virtual instrument by feeling the gestures of each other.

The non real time model is composed of a first set of vibrating structures of 10,000 independent oscillators (*nostalgia of additive synthesis!*), which all the pitches are different and dispersed randomly from 20Hz to 10KHz. These oscillators are geometrically placed radially on the GENESIS workbench at distances inversely proportional to the pitch (in cents) and randomly for the angular positions.

A second set of vibrating structures is composed of interconnected <MAT> modules. For example, there exists a “gong”, modeled as a meshed disk, on which nodes are MAS modules linked hexagonally by REF viscoelastic bonds. The bonds are nonlinear REF in a way to approximate the thin shells non linearities leading to the evolution toward chaos in real gongs or cymbals.

5.1. Spatial Audio Projection

The spatial audio projection is done by means of an “emulator” of the sound dome. It consists of 24 SOF⁸ modules arranged on the workbench in isomorphic positions with the speakers in the auditorium. Each of the 10,000 oscillators is connected to the SOF module to which it is closest. Everything then happens as if a huge “plate” (or a tiny galaxy) of oscillators was above our heads, the lowest pitches appearing on the circumference, the highest towards the center (at the edge of the black hole). The same arrangement adopted for the gong places it above our heads; this time, it is not the heights that are projected into space, but the places of impact on this “Gong-Dome”.

5.2. Reflective Instrumentality - Co-instrumentality

The real time playing is morphologically possible only on objects at human sizes (hands or body). Conversely, it will be always a limit to compute large size objects in real time. Such dilemma has been a wonderful challenge to trigger the design of an “emulator” of gestural TGR on huge non real time models. The idea is to place an exact “copy” of the TGR used in the real time model at the exact same place but in the non real time one. However, this apparently simplest idea requires that the emulated TGR has exactly the same physical properties than the real one! This was achieved, thanks to the metrology process described above as a way to solve a complex inverse problem.

So doing, it is possible to play “off-line”, to play “on-line”, to play “on-line together on real TGR”, and to play

⁷ Claude Cadoz, Mondial Creation 10th november 2018, Micro-Music, Festival, Romans, EASTN-DC European Project led by ACROE.

⁸ A CA SOF module outputs forces from several <LIA> and sent them to an audio channel.

“together on-line” with real and emulated TGR, *with same or ... different playings*.

This opens a large spectrum of dialogs: from the re-designing of a previously made real performance to the design of a gestural narration by “anticipation”, and a possible dialog between both. In the above lies a second way of duality called “*Specular Instrumentality*”

The third form of duality, called “*Inter-Instrumentality*”, consists in virtually coupling two TGRs, for example by way of a CA REF module. One can imagine more complex other coupling than this simplest one. Then, both TGR are, by software, interdependent. Thus, the gesture of an instrumentalist can be felt by the other one (Figure 11): one player can be accompanied or contradicted gesturally by the other, etc. Such gestural cooperation, beyond the usual audio one, is a very new situation, impossible to reach in real world. Within *Quetzalcoatl*, such promising situations are just beginning to be explored.

Figure 11. Inter-Instrumentality in *Quetzalcoatl*.

6. TO CONCLUDE: WRITING THE GESTURE

All of these developments, specifically that of “*ergonic sampling*”, extend the processes of “*writing the gestures*” as a part of a post-scripting situation we are lived today by computer technologies, explored in [14], on which instrumentality and writing are newly so closely and strongly linked.

The gesture itself can be written, through a coherent and transmissible method, without any weakening of the gesture-instrument dialectics. Indeed, the disruption of gesture and instrument could be a breaker deal for music. Here it means that the effect of an “*ergon*” on a TGR, is dependant of the properties of that TGR, as shown by the mathematical formula. Which is anything but a drawback, as it highlights the deeper role of the gestural interaction in music.

Obviously, it points out the necessary quality of haptic systems and accurate methodologies to characterize them qualitatively and quantitatively, in order to stage them on a musical and multi-sensori-motor situation.

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